

ChatGPT vs Google Search: A topic flow analysis of Reddit discussions

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1. Introduction

The rise of Large Language Models (LLMs) has spurred debate on how Artificial Intelligence (AI) impacts changing patterns of search engine use. While LLM applications are distinct from “traditional” search engines, research indicates user preference for LLM-enhanced search, for instance in health settings (Sun et al., 2024), though users sometimes display overreliance on incorrect information when presented by an LLM (Spatharioti et al., 2023). As LLM applications incorporate sophisticated features to incorporate knowledge from external databases and/or search engines with Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) (Gao et al., 2024), the practical distinctions for users might blur, making analysis of how users reflect on these distinctions highly relevant.

This paper seeks to understand how users compare and contrast ChatGPT and Google Search by analysing text data from two subreddits, r/ChatGPT and r/google. The Reddit platform is ideal for this study as its 'subreddit' structure allows for the targeted collection of rich, contextual data from specific communities (Proferes et al., 2021). Reddit has been used to gauge public opinion on ChatGPT, which included comparisons to search engines (Naing & Udomwong, 2024). Text data from r/ChatGPT has been analysed to get insights into the different uses of ChatGPT like writing tasks, meal planning (Choi et al., 2023), how users weigh systems like ChatGPT against established search engines like Google requires further exploration.

Recent API and Data restrictions implemented by Reddit (Reddit, Inc., 2024a, 2024b) present novel challenges to collecting and using data for research. Text data is collected for the period May-2024 to May-2025 using the Python API Wrapper² (PRAW) (Boe, 2010/2023), which is then analysed with the topic model BERTopic³ (Grootendorst, 2020/2025). Topic modelling is used not just to identify themes, but to map the flow of discussion topics, or “topic flow”, across comments made to submissions in the subreddits. That is, instead of collecting, storing and interpreting direct quotes, the topic model results are instead used to map and reconstruct the original conversation and the discussion flow from the original dataset.

The analysis first identifies topics at macro, meso, and micro levels, which are then manually verified to create a comprehensive map of what users discuss. Subsequently, the analysis reconstructs micro level topic threads by linking the original comment structure. This enables the visualization of 'topic flows,' which reveals common conversational patterns by showing which micro-level topics most frequently precede or follow one another in a discussion. This method provides a map of the context and dynamics of the conversation surrounding these topics while ensuring privacy and compliance with the new data and API restrictions

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² PRAW is “a python package that allows for simple access to Reddit's API”, available at <https://github.com/praw-dev/praw>

³ BERTopic is python package and “topic modeling technique that leverages 🧠 transformers and c-TF-IDF to create dense clusters allowing for easily interpretable topics whilst keeping important words in the topic descriptions.”, available at <https://maartengr.github.io/BERTopic>

Preliminary meso-level results reveal discussions on direct comparisons (e.g., ChatGPT vs. Google Search, Gemini, Perplexity), accuracy concerns, specific use cases, translation quality, and environmental costs. This approach offers a valuable contribution to search engine research by analysing user perceptions on third-party platforms within an increasingly restrictive data environment.

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